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IDENTIFYING TRAINING NEEDS OF HEALTHCARE MANAGERS OF UKRAINE

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Ключові слова: *публічне управління та адміністрування, сфера охорони здоров'я, керівні кадри сфери охорони здоров'я, навчання керівних кадрів для системи охорони здоров'я, навчальні програми*

Ключевые слова: *публичное управление и администрирование, сфера здравоохранения, руководящие кадры здравоохранения, обучение руководящих кадров для системы здравоохранения, учебные программы*

Abstract. Identifying training needs of healthcare managers of Ukraine. Bilynska M.M., Suray I.G., Vasiuk N.O., Savina T.V. *Purpose of the article is to determine the training needs of healthcare managers in Ukraine in the specialty "Public administration and management". As the main method, we used a written survey (questionnaire survey) of experts in the field of healthcare, using modern computer technologies. Participation of experts in this study is entirely voluntary. Confidentiality of information is guaranteed by anonymity of the questionnaire. Expert poll of healthcare leaders was conducted in March-April 2020 in order to determine training needs of the specialty "Public administration and management." A total of 54 respondents took part in the expert poll. Majority (96.3%) of respondents need to undergo training in the specialty "Public administration and management" (specialization "Management in the field of healthcare"). The overwhelming majority of them would like to undergo training on the topics: "personnel management in healthcare organizations (leadership, communication management, time management, stress management, self-management, psychological foundations of management in healthcare, etc.)" (64.8%) and "healthcare management" (59.3%). Summarizing results of the study, it has been proved that in order to improve the professional competencies of leaders in the health sector, it is desirable to introduce the training program "Leadership and Management in Health Care", which is aimed at solving problematic issues of management in the field of health protection; application of strategic management in the field of health care, quality management of medical care; obtaining communication skills and building an effective team; effective application of the knowledge gained in the environment is changing rapidly, etc. We believe that improving the mechanisms of training, retraining and raising their qualifications should be an important issue in the development of human resources in health care, especially managers. In particular, this applies to innovative forms of education, including trainings, online training, etc.*

Реферат. Определение потребности в обучении руководителей в области здравоохранения Украины. Белинская М.Н., Сурай И.Г., Васюк Н.О., Савина Т.В. *Целью статьи является определение потребностей в обучении руководителей здравоохранения Украины по специальности «Публичное управление и администрирование». В качестве основного нами использован метод письменного опроса (анкетирование) экспертов в области здравоохранения, с применением современных компьютерных технологий. Участие экспертов в этом исследовании является исключительно добровольным. Конфиденциальность информации гарантирована анонимностью анкеты. Экспертный опрос руководителей сферы здравоохранения нами проведено в марте-апреле 2020 года с целью определения потребности в обучении по специальности «Публичное управление и*

адміністрування». Всього в опросі прийняли участь 54 респондента. Більшість (96,3%) респондентів нуждаются в обученні по спеціальності «Публічне управління і адміністрування» (по спеціалізації «Управління в сфері здравоохранения»). Подавляюча їх частина хотіла б пройти обучение по темам: «Управління персоналом в організації здравоохранения (лідерство, комунікативний менеджмент, тайм-менеджмент, стрес-менеджмент, самоменеджмент, психологічні основи менеджмента в здравоохранении и др.)» (64,8%) і «Менеджмент здравоохранения» (59,3%). Обобщая результаты исследования, доказано, что для повышения профессиональных компетенций руководителей сферы здравоохранения необходимо ввести учебную программу «Лідерство і менеджмент в здравоохранении», которая направлена на решение проблемных вопросов управления в сфере охраны здоровья; применения стратегического управления в сфере здравоохранения, управления качеством медицинской помощи; получение навыков коммуникации и формирования эффективной команды; эффективного применения полученных знаний в среде, которая быстро меняется, и др. Считаем, что основой развития кадрового потенциала здравоохранения, особенно руководителей, должно быть совершенствование механизмов подготовки, переподготовки и повышения их квалификации. В частности, это касается инновационных форм обучения, в т.ч. тренингов, он-лайн обучения и тому подобное.

In recent years, health care reforms in Ukraine, as well as crisis situations, in particular the pandemic (Covid-19), underlines a special role of health care managers, who must quickly make effective management decisions in conditions of uncertainty and lack of resources.

It should be emphasized that the key competencies of health care managers are how and to what extent the manager achieves the expected results in the work in accordance with the objectives [6]. Accordingly, in modern conditions there is a need to train managers in the field of health care in order to develop professional competencies, as well as increase the level of professionalism of managers [7].

Unfortunately, today in the health care system of Ukraine there is a shortage of highly qualified managers who could manage not only the health care facility, but also develop the industry as a whole. The reasons for the low level and quality of management training for the health care system in recent years are the insufficient attention of public authorities to the training (in particular, training) of managerial staff; low level of funding; imperfection of management training programs for the health care system, etc. In order to successfully solve the problem of training health care managers in Ukraine, which is extremely important, it is first necessary to clarify the need for it.

The purpose of the article is to determine the training needs of health care managers in Ukraine in the specialty "Public Administration".

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

The research methodology is based on a set of interconnected and complementary general scientific and special research methods aimed at obtaining objective and reliable results. Among them are both empirical and theoretical methods of scientific research. We believe that in order to achieve the goal of the research, it is the empirical research that is important, which is based primarily on induction

with the subsequent application of the deductive method to generalize the obtained results.

We mainly use the method of written survey (questionnaire) of experts in the field of health care with modern computer technology.

Analysis of research conducted in the health care management system requires additional information about events and phenomena. An objective and informative source of such information is the involvement of respondents as experts – managers (specialists) in the field of health care.

Our chosen methodology is also confirmed by other researchers who note the importance of survey and questionnaire methods in collecting primary information for planning the next steps of needs analysis in educational programs [1], in sociological research during training, retraining and advanced training of heads of public administration, in particular in the field of health care [5]. This methodology allows to determine the individual attitude of respondents to personal and organizational needs and to obtain representative information, it accurately describe the causes of the existing educational need which will give a more reliable forecast of its further development and formulate the best and most effective ways to meet it [4]. The purpose of the expert survey is to obtain the necessary information reflected in the knowledge, opinions and assessments of respondents who are competent persons and have in-depth knowledge of the subject or object of research as well as valuable practical experience in a particular field [3].

Particular attention is paid to the development of the questionnaire, which consists of three parts: introduction (contains information about the purpose of the survey; the person conducting the survey, the time required to conduct the survey, etc.); requisites part (characteristics of the respondent: age, sex, position, category, scientific degree, basic education, special education in management, work experience:

for specialty, in a managerial position, in the civil service) and the main part (questions to the respondent). The questionnaire contains questions about the interest in special education in management and leadership in the field of health care, the feasibility of training courses, trainings, schools, etc., as well as a list of topics which respondents would like to do study and other questions. Each question has a list of suggested variants of answers and it is possible to add your own answer.

Respondents were divided into the following groups: the first group – by the criterion of "availability of special education in management", the second group – by forms of special education in "public administration and administration in the field of health", and the group - by themes of training.

The participation of experts in this study is exclusively voluntary. Confidentiality of information is guaranteed by the anonymity of the questionnaire.

Description of applied methods of statistical analysis. The study uses the statistical method, the method of expert evaluations, the method of questionnaires, the method of graphical analysis, etc., and presents the primary statistical analysis of data – ranking; correlation analysis of data correspondences was performed. One-dimensional data distribution and frequency distribution were

carried out, in particular, on generalization of socio-demographic characteristics of respondents.

The study used information tools to maintain the validity of the results. The results of the study were analyzed using the statistical package "STATISTICA 6.0" and spreadsheet editor "Excel 2013", which allowed to visualize and present data in the form of tables, charts, graphs, as well as to calculate the reliability of the obtained conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Ukraine in March-April of 2020 we conducted an expert survey of health care managers to determine the need for training in the specialty "Public Administration".

A total of 54 respondents took part in the survey (Table). Of these: 66.7% – women, 33.3% – men. The majority of respondents 38.9% – aged 41 to 50 years and 31.5% – from 31 to 40 years. All respondents have higher education, of which 74.1% – medical degree, and only 5.7% – in public administration. Among all respondents: specialists of the highest category – 27.1%, with a degree in science – 43.3%. At the same time, we note that 40.4% of respondents have less than 5 years of experience on a managerial position, and 38.5% – from 5 to 10 years.

Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, %

Sex:	Female - 66.7		Male - 33.3		
Age:	20-30 years 11,1	31-40 years	41-50 years 38,9	51-65 years 14,8	66 and more years 3,7
Higher Education:	Medical 74,1	Legal 5,7	Economic 5,7	Public administration and administration (Public administration) 5,7	Pharmaceutical, biological, engineering and technical 8,8
Category	Scientific degree 43.3 Higher 27.1		I category 16,7	II category 2,1	Not certified 10,8
Work experience in a managerial position	Less than 5 years 40,4	5-10 years 38,5	11-20 years 17,3	More than 20 years 3,8	

Note that answering the question: "Do you have a special education in management?" 63% of respondents answered "yes" (Fig. 1).

Answering the question "Does the availability of special management education affect your career growth?" 61.1% of respondents said that it affects.

70.4% regularly take advanced training courses, trainings, schools, etc. in health management, including 65.1% – once a year, 16.3% - once every three years, 11.6% – once every five years.

According to the respondents, it is important that the greatest motivation for learning was the need to

acquire new knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the work (79.6%); to establish useful connections in the field of professional activity

(55.6%), as well as to apply new knowledge, skills and abilities in public office (48.1%); to contribute to the development of health care in Ukraine 38.9%).

Fig. 1. Availability of special education in management, %

It was found that 96.3% of respondents are interested in special education in public administration and administration in the field of health care,

in particular in the form of trainings (63%), master's program (51.9%), advanced training courses and online learning (44.4%) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Forms of special education in public administration and administration in the field of health care, %

It was found that most respondents would like to study on the following topics:

1. Healthcare management (59.3%).
2. Health economics (48.1%).

3. Health policy and public administration (35.2%).

4. Management of public health (25.9%).
5. Medical and pharmaceutical law (50%).

6. Management of changes in the field of health care (44.4%).

7. Quality management in the field of health care (51.9%).

8. Issues of strategic management and planning of health care organizations (48.1%).

9. Issues of personnel management in the organization of health care (leadership, communicative management, time management, stress management, self-management, psychological foundations of management in health care, etc.) (64.8%).

Note that the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine dated October 31, 2018 № 1977 amended the Directory of Occupations. Issue 78 "Health care", according to which the head of the health care institution – the general director (director) or the

head (head) of the health care institution – will perform exclusively managerial functions and will be engaged in administrative activities, and all medical functions of the head will be performed by the medical director [2]. Therefore, we proposed to determine the attitude to the proposed changes. It was found that 59.3% of respondents believe that such changes should be introduced (Fig. 3).

During the survey, the majority of respondents (57.4%) expressed the opinion on the need to introduce the position of manager in health care and training in the specialty "Health Care Management", 25.9% – believe that there is no such a need, and 16.7% believe that such a need exists only in order to occupy senior positions in health care facilities.

Fig. 3. Attitude of respondents to the order of the Ministry of Health, which will regulate the issue of division of functions of head physicians in Ukraine into two positions - general director and medical director, %

CONCLUSIONS

1. Thus, our expert survey on determining the need for training health care managers in Ukraine in the specialty "Public Administration" gives grounds to draw the following conclusions. The majority (96.3%) of respondents need to study in the specialty "Public Administration" (specialization "Health Care Management"). Most of them would like to be trained on the following topics: "Personnel management in health care organization (leadership, communication management, time management, stress management, self-management, psychological foundations of health care management" and others) (64.8%) and "Healthcare Management" (59.3%).

2. Summarizing the results of the study, it is proved that in order to increase the professional competencies of health care managers it is necessary to introduce the training program "Leadership and Management in Health Care", the mastering of which is aimed at solving problems of health management; application of strategic management in the field of health care, quality management of medical care; gaining communication skills and forming an effective team; effective application of the acquired knowledge in a rapidly changing environment, etc.

3. We believe that the basis for the development of human resources in the field of health care, especially managers, should be the improving mechanisms of training, retraining and advanced training, especially in the direction of innovative forms of education.

Conflict of interest. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Prospects for further research include a comparative analysis of management training programs for the health care system.

REFERENCES

1. Braichenko OD, Sachenko TA, Koniashyna NA. [Monitoring the personal needs of management staff as one of the ways to ensure the effectiveness of their professional development]. Kyiv: NADU; 2013. p. 56. [cited 2020 Aug. 23]. Ukrainian. Available from: <https://divovo.in.ua/institut-pidvishennya-kvalifikaciyi-kerivnih-kadriv-v5.html>
2. [Handbook of qualification characteristics of occupations of employees "Issue 78 Health Care". Order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine of March 29, 2002 No. 117]. [Internet]. 2002. [cited 2020 Aug. 23]. Ukrainian. Available from: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/rada/show/va117282-02>
3. [Expert survey]. [Internet]. [cited 2020 Aug. 23]. Ukrainian. Available from: <http://socioplus.com.ua/the-expert-survey/>
4. Skoromniuk MO, Protasova NH, Ponedilko VH, et al. [Advanced training of civil servants: the study of needs and organization of training]. Lugovyi VI, editor. Ukr. acad. state Department under the President of Ukraine. Kyiv: Publishing UADU; 2000. p. 148. Ukrainian.
5. Savchenko BH. [The use of questionnaires as a method of sociological research to analyze the needs for management training]. [Internet]. 2007. [cited 2020 Aug. 23]. Ukrainian. Available from: <https://kbuapa.kh.ua/>
6. Suray I, et al. Public Administration and Innovation Policy in a Networked Society, International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering. 2019 Nov.;8(4):3604-9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.D7831.118419>
7. Savkov A, Suray I, Kotliar L, Polishchuk L, Bushman I, Vasiuk N. STEM education as the latest philosophy of lifelong learning to develop key competencies of a civil servant. International Journal of Management. 2020;11(2):163-9.

СПИСОК ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

1. Брайченко О. Д., Саченко Т. А., Коняшина Н. А. Моніторинг особистісних потреб управлінських кадрів як один із шляхів забезпечення ефективності їх професійного розвитку: навч.-метод. матеріали. Київ: НАДУ, 2013. 56 с. URL: <https://divovo.in.ua/institut-pidvishennya-kvalifikaciyi-kerivnih-kadriv-v5.html> (дата звернення: 23.08.2020).
2. Довідник кваліфікаційних характеристик професій працівників Вип. 78 «Охорона здоров'я»: Наказ Міністерства охорони здоров'я України від 29.03.2002 р. № 117. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/rada/show/va117282-02> (дата звернення: 23.08.2020).
3. Експертне опитування. URL: <http://socioplus.com.ua/the-expert-survey/> (дата звернення: 23.08.2020).
4. Підвищення кваліфікації державних службовців: вивчення потреби та організація навчання: б. наук. пр. / М. О. Скоромнюк та ін. *Укр. акад. держ. упр. при Президентові України*; ред. В. І. Луговий. Київ: Вид-во УАДУ, 2000. 148 с.
5. Савченко Б. Г. Використання анкетування як методу соціологічного дослідження для аналізу потреб з підвищення кваліфікації управлінських кадрів. URL: <https://kbuapa.kh.ua/> (дата звернення: 23.08.2020).
6. Public Administration and Innovation Policy in a Networked Society / I. Suray et al. *Inter. Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*. 2019. Nov. (Vol. 8, No. 4). P. 3604-3609. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.D7831.118419>
7. STEM education as the latest philosophy of lifelong learning to develop key competencies of a civil servant / A. Savkov et al. *Inter. Journal of Management*. 2020. Vol. 11, No. 2. P. 163-169.

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